

www.bjisrd.com

The Origin, Diagnosis and Modern Clinical Diagnostic Methods of Asthenic Syndrome

Jo‘rayeva Dilbar Khamidovna

Head of the Rehabilitation Department of the Samarkand Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center

Gaffarova Guljahon Ibragimovna, Makhmatov Farhod Egamberdiyevich

Doctor of the Rehabilitation Department of the Samarkand Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center

Uzoqova Oyjamol Narzullayevna

Assistant of the Department of Hematology of the Samarkand State Medical University

***Abstract:** If, under ordinary stress, there is no strength for household chores or work, and even sleep does not bring relief, then this is probably asthenia. This condition can be caused by various factors, from malnutrition to the habit of constantly following the news. In addition, asthenia is a symptom of many diseases. Therefore, if unexplained fatigue occurs, it is important to consult a doctor.*

***Key words:** Asthenia, causes, symptoms, types of syndrome, stages, complications, diagnosis, treatment.*

Introduction

Asthenia (from the Greek *esthénos* - "weak") is a condition in which a person experiences pathological fatigue. Unlike normal fatigue, which occurs during physical or mental exertion, pathological fatigue develops without a pronounced high load and does not go away after rest.

People with asthenia do not tolerate physical and emotional stress well.

This condition is very common and, despite being described in many scientific works, it still lacks a clear definition, classification and description. The truth is that the symptoms of the syndrome can be very diverse and are often subjective, and therefore difficult to measure and systematize.

Features of asthenic syndrome:

the condition lasts a long time, from one to several months;

accompanied by two or more symptoms: headache or muscle pain, dizziness, indigestion, poor sleep, irritability, decreased work capacity;

Fatigue is constantly felt: a person does not remember the moments when he felt cheerful and light.

The International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, 10th revision (ICD-10) does not have a separate code for asthenia, but it is classified among a number of diseases for a reason.

ICD-10 codes that include asthenia:

F4 - neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders;

R53 - restlessness and fatigue;

F48.0 - neurasthenia;

R53 - nonspecific asthenia;

Z73.0 - fatigue syndrome;

F48.8 - psychasthenia;

F06.6 - organic emotionally labile (asthenic) disorder;

G90.8 - Other disorders of the autonomic nervous system;

G93.3 - Fatigue syndrome after viral infection (post-covid asthenia).

Methods: There are cases when the condition develops without any apparent cause. For example, asthenia is often found in tall, thin people. This constitution is characterized by low blood pressure, which also often makes a person feel weak and fatigued.

However, as a rule, asthenia is a compensatory reaction to certain changes: this condition can occur against the background of certain diseases or under the influence of external factors. In fact, asthenia is a consequence of a decrease in the resources of the central nervous system as a result of psycho-emotional overload, stress, excessive physical and social stress, acute and debilitating somatic diseases, such as acute infectious diseases, coronary artery disease, etc. heart disease, chronic viral hepatitis, AIDS, chronic heart failure, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, peptic ulcer, etc. The difference between asthenia and simple physiological fatigue is that even after sufficient rest, a person does not feel fresh and full of strength, does not feel a replenishment of resources for further activity.

Asthenia during or after illness

Asthenia due to illness - temporary or long-term - occurs very often. This is explained by the fact that in many diseases the load on the immune system increases, the active work of which requires a lot of energy from the body. Depending on the illness, normal energy levels may return almost immediately after recovery or only after a few months.

In addition to increasing the load on the body, diseases often lead to biochemical changes, such as a decrease in the level of neurotransmitters - serotonin, norepinephrine, dopamine. These substances transmit signals between the cells of the central and peripheral nervous system and play an important role in regulating mood, emotions, sleep, appetite, behavior, learning and other biological processes. When their concentration decreases, a person feels drowsiness, apathy, anxiety or irritability, chronic fatigue occurs.

Many diseases lead to sleep disorders - this is another possible reason for the development of asthenic syndrome. Sleep is necessary to restore strength and energy. If a person does not regularly get enough sleep and does not have enough quality rest, this will inevitably lead to a deterioration in physical and mental condition.

Diseases and conditions in which asthenic syndrome may occur:

- a. infectious diseases, such as influenza, herpes viral infections, mononucleosis;
- b. chronic diseases of the urinary or digestive system: pyelonephritis, ulcerative colitis;
- c. endocrine system disorders: diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism, Graves' disease;
- d. autoimmune diseases: rheumatoid arthritis;
- e. blood diseases: anemia;
- f. neurological and mental disorders: multiple sclerosis, depressive disorder, dementia, schizophrenia;
- g. oncological diseases;
- h. cardiovascular diseases: hypertension, cardiovascular disease;
- i. lung diseases: tuberculosis, bronchial asthma;
- j. congenital features of the musculoskeletal system;
- k. consequences of birth trauma;
- l. hereditary predisposition to asthenia;
- m. hypovitaminosis;

n. pregnancy, breastfeeding.

Despite the fact that asthenic syndrome can occur against the background of various diseases, viruses directly related to the occurrence of the disease have not yet been identified.

Asthenic syndrome often develops when taking medications. This is because the drugs affect the nervous system and hormone production, disrupting the balance of chemicals and other processes in the body.

Drugs that can cause asthenia:

- antidepressants, especially at the beginning of treatment;
- antiallergic (antihistamine) drugs;
- antiepileptic drugs;
- anti-anemia medications;
- medications to control blood pressure;
- medicines used to treat cancer (e.g. chemotherapy drugs);
- antibiotics.

Medications can cause drowsiness or a decrease in energy levels, either due to their effects or due to individual reactions of the body. If taking medication causes symptoms of asthenia, it is necessary to

inform the doctor about this: perhaps he will be able to choose another drug that does not have such a pronounced asthenic effect.

Asthenia caused by other factors

Most often, asthenia develops in relatively healthy people under the influence of external factors affecting the functioning of the nervous system or metabolism. A distinctive feature of asthenia is that it can occur not only under the influence of the objective environment, but also, for example, under the influence of an imaginary or imagined negative event.

External factors that can cause asthenia:

- a. change time zones;
- b. weather or climate change;
- c. stressful events - starting a new job, moving, wedding, divorce;
- d. post-traumatic stress disorder, such as after a car accident, earthquake, or terrorist attack;
- e. information neurosis due to the overwhelming flow of disturbing news;
- f. work that requires prolonged intellectual or emotional stress, multitasking, and frequent switching of attention;
- g. lack of emotional or physical stress, work without holidays or weekends;
- h. life under a tight schedule, deadlines, constant lack of time;
- i. emotional exhaustion;
- j. recovery from illnesses and injuries;
- k. toxic effects of parasites;
- l. work in hazardous production (vibration, noise, radiation);
- m. low physical activity;
- n. malnutrition;
- o. alcohol abuse;
- p. drug use.

Symptoms of asthenia

The main symptom of asthenia is weakness and fatigue, which occurs without any reason (active phase of the disease, increased physical or intellectual stress) and lasts more than a month. Usually, the decrease in energy levels is accompanied by two or more accompanying symptoms.

Symptoms associated with asthenic syndrome :

- a. memory impairment: events, numbers, and planned activities fly by so quickly and frequently that it often causes anxiety in a person;
- b. decreased concentration - it becomes difficult to focus on work tasks, read a book, and even communicate with other people;
- c. mood instability, increased excitability, tearfulness, moodiness, impatience;
- d. sore throat and other symptoms of ARVI (may occur against the background of decreased immunity caused by asthenia);
- e. pain in the lymph nodes in the neck and armpits;
- f. pain in muscles or joints (develops against the background of physical activity and reduced muscle tone);
- g. tension headache (occurs against the background of an imbalance of neurotransmitters);
- h. lack of energy after sleep: often a person wakes up tired even after a sufficient amount of sleep;
- i. fatigue after minor physical or mental stress;
- j. sleep disorder, insomnia.

Often, symptoms of asthenia lead to the development of new manifestations of the syndrome, and a vicious circle is formed. For example, with a prolonged headache, irritability develops, and with insomnia, deterioration of brain function, daytime sleepiness and other serious complications (depression, anxiety).

Due to the prolonged inflammatory process against the background of biochemical disorders caused by asthenia, a person may experience flu-like symptoms.

Types of asthenic syndrome

There is no single classification of asthenic syndrome, but sources offer different approaches, in which the condition is characterized by its duration, nature of occurrence, and other features.

By duration of asthenia:

- a. long-term (characteristic symptoms last more than 1 month);
- b. chronic (lasting more than 6 months).
- c. According to the circumstances of the incident:
- d. primary - develops as an independent disease, for example, in people prone to low blood pressure;
- e. secondary - develops against the background of diseases, taking certain medications;
- f. reactive - occurs during conditioned physiological changes, such as pregnancy or breastfeeding, against the background of stress, vitamin deficiency, weather changes, or other factors.

Results: symptomatic - there is an objective reason for the development of symptoms, such as a disease or adverse environmental influences;

psychogenic - develops as a reaction to an expected or imagined negative event, for example, when a person is afraid of getting sick or losing property.

Some medical sources distinguish three types of conditions in which a person experiences pathological fatigue: asthenia itself, asthenic syndrome and chronic pathological fatigue. Asthenia includes fatigue caused by various diseases - infectious, endocrine. Asthenic syndrome - fatigue caused by overload, surgery or taking medications. Chronic pathological fatigue is understood as a feeling of constant weakness that occurs independently without any apparent reason. This condition is called chronic fatigue syndrome, it develops against the background of infectious diseases (usually viral), intoxications, cardiovascular pathology or due to genetic characteristics of the central nervous system;

Stages of asthenia

There are three stages of asthenia. The first is accompanied by increased irritability and overwork. A person turns on for minor reasons or almost unexpectedly. At the same time, weakness and decreased performance are moderate.

In the second stage, work and household chores become more difficult for the person. Irritability remains, but often the attack of anger ends in tears; Gradually, irritation turns into anxiety, the person feels powerless and unable to cope with tasks or situations.

The third stage is accompanied by significant fatigue. The person moves little and cannot concentrate even on simple tasks. At this stage, irritability, as a rule, disappears: there is no strength to swear, to put things in order, or to prove that you are right.

Complications of asthenia

Long-term asthenia leads to a significant decrease in endurance and productivity. Even simple tasks or exercises become unusual. The body's endurance decreases.

After a decrease in mobility, symptoms of the cardiovascular, endocrine, and nervous systems begin to develop. Tachycardia and hypertension may appear or increase, metabolism slows down, muscle strength decreases, and the load on bones and joints increases.

Asthenia also causes disturbances at the level of physiological processes. For example, a decrease in the activity of T-killer cells, which are cells of the immune system responsible for destroying pathogens and cancer cells, has been noted. Slowing down their work can increase the risk of infectious diseases and cancer.

Lack of energy, previous stress or illness can lead to disruption of the hypothalamus, a part of the brain that plays an important role in regulating the hormonal system. At the first signs of asthenia, the hypothalamus registers this condition and signals the need to increase appetite, produce energy-supporting hormones, or activate other processes related to energy metabolism. However, if this condition persists for a long time, hormonal imbalance develops, the hypothalamus begins to react even to minimal stimuli, and the symptoms of asthenia become even more severe.

Over time, a person's cognitive functions deteriorate and social adaptation may develop: difficulties arise with work, communication, and hobbies; he becomes self-reliant, feels uncomfortable around other people, and stops communicating with friends.

Diagnosis of asthenic syndrome

Diagnosis of asthenic syndrome is carried out by the method of exclusion, taking into account the presence of a provoking factor in the anamnesis: the doctor conducts a full examination to identify conditions or diseases that could lead to the development of pathological fatigue. Finding the cause may take a long time and require a series of examinations.

Examination and history taking

Diagnosis begins with a physical examination: the doctor assesses the patient's appearance and muscle tone, measures pulse, blood pressure, palpates the thyroid gland and abdominal organs, checks for swelling of the arms and legs, assesses the condition of the skin and hair. All this allows him to identify or exclude signs of metabolic disorders, diseases of the endocrine, urinary, cardiovascular and other systems.

The doctor will then analyze the patient's medical history to determine if they have any chronic diseases or a genetic predisposition to them. He will ask questions about the current state: at what moments does fatigue manifest itself most, what activities accompany it, and how long ago did it appear.

Instrumental and laboratory diagnostics

Laboratory tests are an important step in diagnosing asthenia. Tests can identify hidden inflammatory processes, hormonal disorders, or chronic diseases.

Asthenic syndrome can develop in many diseases, and it is important to identify them at the time of diagnosis so that treatment is effective and the result is long-lasting.

To diagnose depression, a doctor will take a medical history and conduct an interview to determine the patient's mental state. The doctor may also order a series of laboratory tests to rule out possible physical causes, such as vitamin deficiencies.

Genetically determined need for vitamins and minerals (A, C, D, E, K, B2, B6, B9, B12, Omega-3, magnesium, zinc, iron, choline)

To check the functioning of the thyroid gland, determine its size, shape and structure, the doctor palpates it, prescribes tests and ultrasound. If nodules are found in the thyroid gland, it is sent for biopsy (taking a tissue sample of the nodule through a small puncture and examining it under a microscope).

Thyroid gland, screening

A comprehensive study that helps diagnose thyroid diseases and monitor their treatment. Recommended for people at risk of thyroid diseases, including residents of regions with low natural iodine content in drinking water, and patients with thyroid diseases.

To rule out iron deficiency anemia, the doctor will ask the patient about the nature of the fatigue and perform a physical examination: paying attention to the discoloration of the skin and mucous membranes, brittleness and brittle nails. Tests can help identify abnormalities in the composition of the blood.

Conclusion: Complete blood count with leukocyte count and ESR, smear microscopy (venous blood) for pathological changes in leukocyte count

To determine the cause of anemia, instrumental studies may be required: gastroscopy, colonoscopy, pelvic ultrasound. They help to eliminate hidden bleeding, which can also cause anemia.

Asthenia can be caused by various sleep disorders, including obstructive sleep apnea, a condition in which breathing stops for short periods during sleep. The disorders can be difficult to diagnose. Screening involves instrumental methods, including sleep quality checks and questionnaires, as well as the insertion of sensors to assess the processes that occur in the body during sleep.

Immunodeficiency states, such as HIV or congenital diseases of the immune system, are diagnosed using general clinical, immunological, and genetic studies.

Immune status (screening) (phagocytic activity of leukocytes, cellular immunity, total immunoglobulin IgE, immunoglobulins IgA, IgM, IgG)

List of used literature:

1. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 282-288.
2. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
3. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 545-550.
4. Begbudiyev M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 551-557.

5. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 558-563.
6. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
7. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 409-414.
8. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 898-903.
9. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.
10. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 240-244.
11. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 385-391.
12. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 245-251.
13. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 230-235.
14. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 258-264.
15. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 392-397.
16. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 186-191.
17. Prostyakova N. et al. Changes in the postpsychotic period after acute polymorphic disorder //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 356-360.
18. Prostyakova N. et al. Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 158-165.
19. Prostyakova N. et al. Sadness and loss reactions as a risk of forming a relationship together //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 252-257.
20. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular diseaseisomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 166-172.
21. Rotanov A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 267-272.

22. Rotanov A. et al. Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 309-315.
23. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.
24. Rotanov A. et al. Social, socio-cultural and behavioral risk factors for the spread of hiv infection //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 49-55.
25. Rotanov A. et al. Suicide and epidemiology and risk factors in oncological diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 398-403.
26. Sedenkov V. et al. Clinical and socio-demographic characteristics of elderly patients with suicide attempts //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 273-277.
27. Sedenkov V. et al. Modern methods of diagnosing depressive disorders in neurotic and affective disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 361-366.